

24 **Abstract**

25 Structure properties of alginate and glycerol hydrogels (93:7 v/v) functionalized with
26 gallic acid (0.1, 0.5 and 0.8 % (w/v)) were evaluated as plastic alternative for food
27 packaging. A thorough characterization of these hydrogels was performed, evaluating
28 their physico-mechanical, optical, and functional properties, particularly for potential
29 applications in food packaging. FTIR analysis confirmed interactions between the
30 hydrogel matrix and gallic acid, highlighting the formation of hydrogen bonds. The BET
31 method and high-resolution scanning electron microscopy (HRSEM) further verified the
32 homogeneity of the hydrogel surfaces. The inclusion of gallic acid led to increased
33 thickness, permeability, and swelling capacity. However, ultimate tensile strength and
34 fracture toughness significantly decreased, especially in hydrogels containing the highest
35 gallic acid concentration (0.8%). Functionalized hydrogels exhibited enhanced
36 antioxidant activity, as demonstrated by DPPH and FRAP assays. Hydrogels with 0.5%
37 gallic acid showed a 4.4–4.8-fold increase in antioxidant activity, while those with 0.8%
38 gallic acid achieved a 7.0–7.3-fold enhancement. The release of gallic acid from the
39 hydrogels followed a dose-dependent pattern, with peak release occurring within 1–2
40 hours. These findings suggest that alginate-based hydrogels functionalized with gallic
41 acid offer a promising approach for the controlled release of bioactive compounds,
42 presenting potential applications in innovative packaging solutions.

43

44

45 **Keywords:**

46 Hydrogels, alginate, gallic acid, antioxidant activity, food packaging, plastic replacement

47 **1. Introduction**

48 The development of new materials built with sustainable components is one of the
49 new challenges facing the scientific community as new environmental policies enacted
50 by various international institutions aim to reduce environmental impact and the efficient
51 production of materials (European Commission, Circular Economy Action Plan,
52 Luxembourg, 2020). Plastic continues to dominate food packaging due to its cost-
53 effectiveness, durability, and versatility. However, growing global awareness of the
54 environmental harm caused by plastic pollution has spurred increased scrutiny and efforts
55 to minimize its use. In line with the Sustainable Development Goals which emphasizes
56 sustainable resource management, the agri-food industry and scientific community are
57 actively promoting sustainable practices in packaging. This includes exploring alternative
58 materials to plastic that can effectively preserve food products while adopting a more
59 environmentally friendly approach. On this scenario, hydrogels have been claimed as
60 promising materials due to their physical and mechanical properties.

61 Hydrogels are a kind of advanced materials derived from wet gels subjected to drying
62 process that removes water trapped in the three-dimensional structure while preserving
63 network scaffold (Smirnova and Gurikov, 2018) resulting in solid materials with low
64 density ($0.003 - 0.15 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$), high porosity (80 – 99 %), large surface areas (500 – 1000
65 $\text{m}^2 \text{ g}$) and amorphous structures in most cases (Pierre and Pajonk, 2022). They are
66 nanostructured solid materials derived from inorganic gels: chalcogens, silica... (Kang et
67 al., 2020; Zhao et al., 2020) or organic ones: graphene, proteins, polysaccharides...
68 (Kashyap et al., 2020; Kleemann et al., 2020; Selmer et al., 2019; Wei et al., 2020; Zhu,
69 2019) or a mixture of them resulting in hybrid hydrogels (Chang et al., 2022; Horvat et
70 al., 2019). Although silica hydrogels are by far the most studied and commercially
71 successful for many applications (Adhikary et al., 2021; Aragón-Gutierrez et al., 2020;

72 Chen et al., 2020; Lamy-Mendes et al., 2021), a growing interest is aroused by hydrogels
73 with reduced environmental impact materials.

74 In this sense, polysaccharides are a clear example of sustainable, green, non-toxic
75 and biocompatible material for developing novel hydrogels. In addition, these natural
76 polymers are characterised by abundant functional groups which enable them to be loaded
77 with desired substances such as bioactive compounds or drugs which can be released in
78 a controlled manner over time (Chen and Zhang, 2019; Coldebella et al., 2021; Niknia et
79 al., 2020). Consequently, the functionalisation of polysaccharide-based hydrogels is
80 unfolding fresh applications in biomedicine as scaffolds for controlled drug delivery
81 (Gorshkova et al., 2018), in food packaging to enhance the preservation of foodstuff
82 (Nešić et al. 2018; López de Dicastillo et al., 2016) or even in cosmetic field as healing
83 materials (Vidal et al., 2020).

84 The incorporation of active substances into polysaccharide-bases hydrogels can
85 be performed by several methods. Wet impregnation is one of the most used in which gel
86 constituents are in contact with the desired components for loading before or after the
87 gelling process prior to solvent removal (Selvasekaran and Chidambaram, 2021).
88 Consequently, hydrogels functionalisation and controlled release are strongly conditioned
89 to the solubility between the compounds to be loaded and the solvent used during
90 impregnation and the interactions of the component with the polymeric scaffolds of the
91 hydrogel (Chen and Zhang, 2019; Niknia et al., 2020; Dos Santos et al., 2020). Therefore,
92 the wide variety of polysaccharide available for hydrogels development as well as active
93 components loaded into structures make possible the design of new tailor-made materials
94 with customised properties.

95 In this sense, alginate is a promising polysaccharide to produce functionalised
96 hydrogels. Alginate is a linear anionic and hydrophilic polysaccharide obtained from

97 marine algae and built from mannuronic and guluronic acids which present many
98 carboxylic and hydroxyl groups (Leyva-Jiménez et al., 2023). However, the alginate-
99 based hydrogels present some mechanical limitations such as low elasticity being prone
100 to break easily (Biao et al., 2019). For this purpose, glycerol was added as a plasticizer to
101 improve the flexibility and mechanical properties of the hydrogels, making them more
102 suitable for various applications.

103 Carboxylic and hydroxyl groups of both substances not only enhance the gelling
104 properties of alginate and glycerol with polyvalent metal ions but also allow the
105 incorporation of active compounds, particularly polyphenols, inside the polymeric
106 network improving hydrogel mechanical properties as well as conferring antioxidant and
107 antimicrobial properties (Biao et al., 2019; Carbone et al., 2021; Fabra et al., 2018) or
108 even acting as controlled delivery materials (Fernández-Ponce et al., 2021; Lovskaya et
109 al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2021). According to previous reports, some functional groups of
110 phenolic compounds can interact with the polymeric network of hydrogels by
111 electrostatic interactions (hydrogen bonds, Van der Waals forces...). Due to the weak
112 interactions between the polymeric matrix and phenolic compounds, a controlled release
113 is achievable. This prolongs the bioactivity of the phenolic compounds over time, in
114 contrast to free bioactive compounds (Lovskaya et al., 2015).

115 However, incorporating phenolic compounds into hydrogels presents several
116 challenges, such as accurately determining the optimal amount of phenolic compound or
117 phenolic extract to ensure the hydrogel's characteristics and properties remain intact,
118 while also providing a sufficient concentration to enhance bioactivity and deliver
119 antioxidant and antimicrobial effects through controlled release. Literature suggests
120 limiting concentrations to no more than 2–3%, as higher amounts may alter the polymeric
121 chains and adversely affect the hydrogel's mechanical performance (Biao et al., 2019).

122 However, the percentage of bioactive compound should be tailored not only to the nature
123 and structure of the phenolic compound but also to the intended application of the
124 hydrogel.

125 Our hypothesis is that alginate hydrogels can be functionalized with pure gallic
126 acid, a naturally abundant, simple phenolic compound with three hydroxyl groups, known
127 for its proven antioxidant properties, to create new sustainable materials appropriate for
128 food packaging as plastic replacement. The effects of varying concentrations of pure
129 gallic acid (0.1, 0.5 and 0.8 %) on the hydrogel's characteristics and properties were
130 evaluated. A comprehensive characterization of gallic acid-functionalized alginate
131 hydrogels was conducted including assessments of mechanical performances, water
132 vapor permeability, swelling behaviour and the surface structure via scanning electron
133 microscopy (SEM). Additionally, the hydrogels' loading capacity, antioxidant properties,
134 and controlled release of gallic acid were analyzed, providing essential insights for
135 designing their future applications in food packaging.

136 **2. Material and Methods**

137 **2.1. Materials and reagents**

138 Sodium alginate was purchased from DuPont Nutrition As (Billingstad, Norway)
139 with weight average molecular weight of 122 ± 15 KDa. The ratio of guluronic acid (G)
140 to mannuronic acid (M) units in sodium alginate was 68/32 and the polydispersity index,
141 ratio of weight average molecular weight to number average molecular weight was 1.27
142 (data was provided by the manufacturer). On the other hand, glycerol, calcium chloride
143 and gallic acid (high purity grade ≥ 98.0 %) from Sigma Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany).
144 Additionally, purified water was obtained by a Milli-Q system from Millipore (Bedford,
145 MA, USA). For total phenolic content and antioxidant capacity determinations, methanol,
146 Folin-Ciocalteu, sodium carbonate, DPPH: 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl radical,

147 TPTZ: 2,4,6-tris(pyridin-2-yl)-1,3,5-triazine, ferric chloride, ferrous sulfate, sodium
148 acetate, acetic acid and hydrochloric acid were purchased from Sigma Aldrich
149 (Steinheim, Germany). For the assessment of gallic acid release, sodium chloride,
150 potassium chloride, sodium phosphate monobasic and potassium phosphate dibasic were
151 bought from Sigma Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany). All chemical used were at least of
152 reagent grade.

153 **2.2. Preparation of alginate and gallic acid-functionalized alginate hydrogels**

154 For the preparation of hydrogels, a 1% (w/v) aqueous solution of sodium alginate
155 was previously dissolved at room temperature until complete dissolution. After that,
156 alginate solution was mixed with glycerol at ratio 93:7 v/v and stirred until reach a
157 homogeneous solution. With the aim of functionalizing alginate hydrogels, 0.1, 0.5 and
158 0.8 % (w/v) of gallic acid was added and dissolved in the alginate-glycerol mixture. The
159 mixtures were then poured into plastic moulds (20 x 10 x 1 cm) and gelled with a 0.2 M
160 calcium chloride solution. For this purpose, the calcium chloride solution (20 % v/v) was
161 sprayed on the surface of the mould and the gel formed was left to stabilise for about 20
162 minutes. After this, the hydrogel was dried by forced air in a convection oven at 35 °C
163 until total loss of moisture. Finally, the films were removes and stored in a desiccator
164 until further assays.

165 **2.3. Physicomechanical characterization of hydrogels**

166 **2.3.1. Thickness**

167 The thickness of the hydrogels was evaluated using a digital micrometer (0 - 25 mm
168 ± 0.001) (Palmer Wahl, Asheville, NC, USA). The average thickening value of the films
169 was determined by taking 6 measurements at random positions in the gel.

170 **2.3.2. Water vapor permeability**

171 The water vapor permeability (WVP) of alginate-based films was measured
172 gravimetrically (ASTM E96/E96M-16 method) following the wet cup method, a standard
173 test method for water transmission of materials (ASTM Committee, 2016). Briefly, 10
174 mL of distilled water was placed in a VF2200-606 permeability cup (TQC Sheen,
175 Molennbaan, Netherlands) with an inner diameter of 3.5 cm. Then, dried films were cut
176 with a surface of 10 cm² and placed in the mouth of the cup. This system was closed and
177 sealed with parafilm in order to warrant the pass of water vapor through the film. Finally,
178 the cups were placed in a desiccator with silica gel keeping constant the temperature at
179 21 ± 1 °C and ensuring a relative humidity of 0 % inside the desiccator. In order to ensure
180 the reproducibility, the temperature was registered along the experiment. The moisture
181 losses of the permeability cup were measured by weighing the cups each hour for 8 hours.
182 The WVP (g/KPa h m) was then determined using the following equations:

$$183 \quad WVT = \frac{\left(\frac{\Delta G}{t}\right) \times x}{A}$$

184 Eq. 1

185 Where water vapor transmission (WVT) was determined using the slope of weight
186 loss in the permeability cup during the assay ($\Delta G/t$) and expressed as g/h. Moreover, the
187 film thickness (x) in meters and the permeation area (A) in m² of the film were also used
188 for determining the WVT which was expressed as g/h m.

$$189 \quad WVP = \frac{WVT}{S \times (HR1 - HR2)}$$

190 Eq. 2

191 For determining the water vapor permeability WVP, the saturation vapor pressure
192 (S) at test temperature (21°C ± 1) in kPa (2.488 kPa at 21°C) and the difference humidity

193 across both sides of the films inside the desiccator (HR1 = 0 %) and inside the permeation
194 cup (HR2 =100%) were used. All experiments were performed in triplicate and the results
195 are shown as an average and expressed in g/kPa h m.

196 **2.3.3. Mechanical properties**

197 Mechanical tests were carried out on a Mecmesin MultiTest-i 2.5-I dynamic
198 mechanical analyser (Mecmesin, West Sussex, UK) at room temperature. Tensile tests
199 were carried out on hydrogels prepared on a mould made of Teflon®, which meets the
200 ISO 37 standard. Samples were anchored by tweezers on the analyser and uniaxially
201 stretched at 50 mm/min until their breaking point, using a cell load of 50 N. Ultimate
202 Tensile Strength (UTS), Youngs's Modulus (YM) and Fracture Toughness (FT) were
203 determined. Firstly, UTS was determined as the maximum pressure value supported by
204 the hydrogel just before break expressed in MPa. The Young's modulus, that indicates
205 the hydrogel elasticity, was calculated from the slope of the linear range of the stress-
206 strain curve (between 2 % and 10 % of strain) and expressed as MPa. Finally, the
207 critical stress intensity of a sharp crack where propagation of the crack suddenly becomes
208 rapid and unlimited (Fracture toughness, FT), was determined from the area under the
209 curve in the linear range between 0 and 10 % strain. FT was expressed as the energy
210 absorbed by the gel in KJ/m³. The experiments were performed at least in triplicate.

211 **2.3.4. Swelling degree**

212 Swelling studies were carried out by immersing the vacuum-dried hydrogels cut into
213 1 cm diameter circles in Milli-Q water (pH = 7) at room temperature. The samples were
214 weighed at established time intervals, finalising the measures when hydrogels had a
215 constant weight. In order to avoid measurement errors by water weight, excess water was
216 removed using a paper filter before each measure. The swelling degree was calculated by
217 the following equation:

218
$$\text{Swelling Degree} = \frac{W_t - W_o}{W_o}$$

219 Eq.3

220 where W_t is the weight of the hydrogels at each time and W_o is the weight of the
221 hydrogels. All experiments were performed at least in triplicate and the results are
222 expressed as weight gain in percentages of one.

223 **2.3.5. Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) experimental setup**

224 The total surface-area concentration and the amount of nitrogen gas required to
225 condensate a monolayer was measured experimentally using BET equipment through
226 isotherms of adsorption and desorption and the distribution of the size of pores. These
227 experiments were measured in a Gemini VII instrument (Micromeritics, GA, USA);
228 Nitrogen gas was used as an adsorbate and the temperature at which the tests were
229 performed was the temperature of liquid nitrogen (-195.79°C). For this test, the samples
230 were degassed prior to the adsorption measurements.

231 **2.3.6. Scanning electron microscopy**

232 The surface structure and morphology of the films were evaluated by high-resolution
233 scanning electron microscopy (HRSEM) using a Gemini SEM 500 (Zeiss, Germany). The
234 analyses were performed on stable hydrogel samples that were lyophilized overnight after
235 being frozen to avoid pressure disturbances during the measurement due to the release of
236 water vapour that may be contained in the gel. The sample was observed under high
237 vacuum conditions and an accelerated voltage of 3kV. At least six micrographs were
238 taken per film and those showing the typical surface morphology of each sample were
239 selected.

240 **2.3.7. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)**

241 To understand the thermal degradation during film storage, hydrogels were subjected
242 to thermal stability assays. Thermogravimetric analysis was carried out in a Q50
243 equipment (TA Instruments, DE, USA). The completely swollen hydrogels (10 mg) were
244 frozen and lyophilised in a Telstar Lyoquest freeze dryer for 24h (condenser temperature
245 -80°C) (Telstar, Barcelona, Spain). The analysis was based on an isothermal under N_2
246 atmosphere at 100°C for 20 min and the following temperature ramp of 10°C each minute
247 until it gets 800°C .

248 **2.3.8. Fourier transform infrared analysis.**

249 The interaction among the components of the alginate-based films and the gallic acid
250 were determined by an IR spectrometer which were recorded on a FT-IR IRAffinity-1S
251 equipment (Shimadzu Scientific Instruments, Japan) at room temperature. Hydrogels
252 were vacuum dried before analysis. The infrared spectra of the film samples were taken
253 between the wavelength 4000 cm^{-1} to 400 cm^{-1} using a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} .

254 **2.4. Optical characterization of hydrogels**

255 **2.4.1. Light transparency and opacity**

256 The light transmittance of alginate based hydrogels was evaluated at a wavelength of
257 600 nm using a UV-visible spectrometer (Helyos Gamma, Thermo, UK) with an empty
258 test cell as the reference according to (Biao et al., 2019). All films were prepared, at least,
259 in triplicate cutting $4\text{ cm} \times 1\text{ cm}$ rectangles and placed in the outside face of the cell for
260 each determination. Each sample was analysed 6 times, and the results were showed as
261 an average of the % of transmittance that pass thought the gel. The opacity value was
262 obtained using the same cut films and the value were expressed as a ratio between the
263 absorbance value at 600 nm and the film thickness (mm).

264 **2.4.2. Colorimetric measurements**

265 The colorimetric assays were performed using a TR500 colorimeter (Lovibond,
266 Hyderabad, India). The tristimulus colour parameters were expressed according to
267 CIELAB space colour (CIE 1976 L* a* b*). In this sense, lightness reflected the black
268 (L* = 0) or white (L*100), redness (a* = +100) or greenness (a* = - 80) and the yellowness
269 (b* = + 70) or blueness (b* = - 80) of each film. In order to determine the total colour
270 difference between hydrogels (ΔE), the following formula was used:

$$271 \quad \Delta E = \sqrt{(\Delta a^*)^2 + (\Delta b^*)^2 + (\Delta L^*)^2}$$

272 Eq.4

273 Where Δa^* , Δb^* , ΔL^* , are the differences between the colour factors of the control
274 film (alginate-glycerol base hydrogel) and the hydrogels functionalised (0.1, 0.5 and 0.8
275 % w/v) with gallic acid. Measurements were obtained at six points on each film, and the
276 results were expressed as the mean of the results obtained.

277 **2.5. Functional characterization of hydrogels**

278 **2.5.1. Total phenolic content**

279 The total phenolic content of hydrogels was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu
280 colorimetric method according to Firoznejhad et al., 2023, with slight modifications
281 (Firoznejhad et al., 2023). Firstly, the film extract was obtained dissolving 0.1 g of
282 hydrogel in 10 mL of methanol, keeping constant agitation at 200 rpm for 24 h. Each
283 extraction procedure was performed in triplicate. Then, 10 μ L of hydrogel extract, water
284 (blank) or standard (calibration curve) was mixed with 600 μ L of water and 50 μ L of
285 Folin-Ciocalteu's phenol reagent. After 10 minutes, 150 μ L of sodium carbonate (20 %
286 w/v) and 190 μ L of water were added to reach a final volume of 1 mL and kept in darkness
287 for 2h. After that, the absorbance was read at 760 nm against blank in a Synergy HI
288 hybrid microreader (Biotek, Germany). A gallic acid calibration curve (5-150 μ g/mL)

289 was used in order to determine the amount of gallic acid incorporated in the gallic acid-
290 functionalized alginate hydrogels. The total phenolic content was expressed as mg of
291 gallic acid/g of hydrogel. All assays were done in triplicate.

292

293 **2.5.2. Antioxidant properties**

294 **2.5.2.1. DPPH radical scavenging activity.**

295 The reduction of the radical DPPH was performed according to Leyva-Jimenez et al.
296 2020. Briefly, 10 μ L of previous film extract or gallic acid solution (5-125 μ g/mL) were
297 dissolved in 990 μ L of DPPH methanolic solution (40 μ L/mL) and incubated in darkness
298 and at room temperature. After that, the absorbance was evaluated at 517 nm, and the
299 obtained results were expressed as mg of gallic acid/g of hydrogel. All experiments were
300 performed in triplicate.

301 **2.5.2.2. Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power assay**

302 The Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP) was carried out according to Benzie
303 and Strain et al., 1996 with some modifications. A ferric complex of TPTZ (15.62 mg)
304 and ferric chloride (16.22 mg) were mixed in 50 mL acetate buffer 0.3M (pH 3.6). For
305 these antioxidant assays, a FeSO_4 calibration curve (0.09 - 1.045 μ M) was used. A 40 μ L
306 of hydrogel extract, blank solution (methanol) or standard solution were added to 250 μ L
307 of previous ferric complex. After 4 minutes of incubation at 37 $^\circ$ C in dark, the absorbance
308 was measured at 593 nm and results were expressed as the antioxidant capacity of mMol
309 of FeSO_4 equivalents/g of hydrogel. All determinations were performed in triplicate.

310 **2.5.3. Release of gallic acid**

311 The release of gallic acid by the hydrogels was indirectly assessed by the
312 measurement of DPPH radical scavenging activity. For this purpose, 10 mg of each

313 hydrogel were mixed with 1 mL of phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) at $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. A 500
314 μL of solution was collected at different times (0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 8 and 24 hours) and kept
315 in refrigeration until assay described in 2.5.2.1 section. All experiments were developed
316 in triplicate and the results were expressed in mg of gallic acid/g of hydrogel.

317 **2.6. Statistical analysis**

318 Data were handled by SPSS v.15. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) at 95%
319 confidence level ($p \leq 0.05$) was used to determine statistically significant differences
320 among hydrogels parameters. Two post-hoc multiple comparison methods were
321 employed depending on the result of the homogeneity of variances test of the results
322 obtained: Tukey post-hoc analysis was used when the variances were homogeneous,
323 otherwise, T3 Dunnet was applied to determine the statistical differences.

324

325 **3. Results and Discussion**

326 **3.1. Physicomechanical characterization of hydrogels.**

327 Hydrogels derived from polysaccharides are known for their porous structure, low
328 density, biocompatibility and remarkable sustainable properties. However, the
329 incorporation of other substance such as gallic acid, an antioxidant agent, can lead to
330 changes in the structural properties of these macromolecular structures. In an exploration
331 to understand the effects of different concentrations of gallic acid on the physical and
332 mechanical properties of alginate hydrogels, a detailed comparative analysis was
333 conducted. Table 1 provides an array of comparative metrics for the alginate hydrogel
334 devoid of gallic acid with those functionalized with different concentrations of gallic acid.
335 The evaluated properties included thickness, water vapor permeability (WVP), swelling
336 degree, ultimate tensile strength (UTS), Young's modulus (YM) and fracture toughness
337 (FT).

338 Table 1. Physicomechanical characterization of alginate and gallic acid-functionalized alginate hydrogels

Hydrogels	Thickness (μm)	WVP $\times 10^{-5}$ (g/KPa h m)	Swelling Degree	UTS (MPa)	YM (MPa)	FT (KJ/m ³)	BET Area (m ² /g)	Pore Radius (nm)
Alg-Gly (93:7)	92 \pm 6 ^c	1.97 \pm 0.07 ^c	1.7 \pm 0.6 ^a	2.2 \pm 0.1 ^a	5.6 \pm 0.5 ^a	732 \pm 77 ^a	7.48	1.52
Alg-Gly (93:7), Gallic acid 0.1 %	114 \pm 7 ^b	3.4 \pm 0.2 ^b	6.3 \pm 1.0 ^b	1.9 \pm 0.2 ^a	5.4 \pm 0.7 ^a	596 \pm 48 ^{a,b}	6.01	1.53
Alg-Gly (93:7), Gallic acid 0.5 %	114 \pm 6 ^b	3.24 \pm 0.02 ^a	4.7 \pm 0.1 ^b	2.0 \pm 0.3 ^a	5.5 \pm 0.8 ^a	423 \pm 27 ^b	7.29	1.71
Alg-Gly (93:7), Gallic acid 0.8 %	140 \pm 4 ^a	3.40 \pm 0.08 ^b	5.0 \pm 0.8 ^b	1.10 \pm 0.02 ^b	5.3 \pm 0.6 ^a	214 \pm 64 ^c	13.83	1.72

339

340 Alg: Alginate; Gly: Glycerol; WVP: Water Vapor Permeability; UTS: Ultimate Tensile Strength; YM: Young's Modulus; FT: Fracture Toughness;

341 BET: Brunauer-Emmett-Teller method

342 Values with different superscripts in the same column denote significant differences among aerogels according to the Tukey post-hoc analysis ($p \leq$

343 0.05) when variances were homogenous, or according to T3 Dunnet post-hoc analysis ($p \leq 0.05$) for non-homogenous variances

344

345 3.1.1. Thickness, water vapor permeability and swelling degree

346 Evidence from our data and insights from various papers converge, illuminating a
347 consistent positive correlation between the concentration of gallic acid and the increased
348 thickness of alginate hydrogel films, a consensus echoed by other authors (Gan and Chin,
349 2021). The thickness increased from $92 \pm 6 \mu\text{m}$ for the base film to $140 \pm 4 \mu\text{m}$ for the
350 film with 0.8 % gallic acid, denoting a substantial thickening of approximately 52 %.

351 Based on these results, it seems that gallic acid could be interacting with the alginate
352 and glycerol, possibly leading to more cross-linking or layering within the material, which
353 could account for the increased thickness. This fact was supported by Li et al., 2019,
354 which discussed the fabrication of mechanically-strong alginate/clay hydrogels and the
355 effects of pH adjustment on their properties (Li et al., 2019). Additionally, a higher water
356 adsorption rate, influenced by the presence of gallic acid, is also observed to contribute
357 to this thickening effect. The augmented water-holding capacity facilitates a more
358 pronounced swelling of the hydrogel films, compounding the effects of enhanced cross-
359 linking and layering to result in a notable increase in thickness since larger gaps between
360 polymeric chains remained after gel drying. This observation is in line with another study
361 that indicates sodium alginate hydrogel as an appropriate material to load high amounts
362 of phenolic acid compounds, such as gallic acid, showcasing its potential for increased
363 thickness and water adsorption capacity (Dos Santos et al., 2020). This observation aligns
364 with findings reported in existing literature, both with gallic acid and similar compounds,
365 further validating the correlation between gallic acid concentration and increased
366 thickness of the alginate hydrogel films (Gan and Chin, 2021; Pereira et al., 2013).

367 This fact should be taken into account since thicker hydrogel film may offer better
368 insulation properties due to its increased volume and more substantial structural integrity.
369 Manzocco et al., 2021 underscored this by discussing the potential of hydrogels as novel
370 packaging materials for food, emphasizing their low density and high porosity (Manzocco
371 et al., 2021). However, it's essential to consider that thicker hydrogel might also lead to
372 reduced flexibility, which could limit their applicability in flexible or dynamic
373 environments. This is a crucial aspect to weigh when considering the balance between
374 insulation and flexibility. In addition, an increase in thickness might also affect other
375 hydrogel properties like permeability and transparency, an area that warrants further
376 exploration to optimize the multifunctional utility of hydrogels in varied application
377 scenarios (Selvasekaran and Chidambaram, 2021; Batista et al., 2019; Zhou et al., 2021).

378 On the other hand, the water vapor permeability of the alginate hydrogel developed
379 was $1.97 \cdot 10^{-5}$ g/Kpa h m, less permeable than similar hydrogels previously studied (Biao
380 et al., 2019; Choi et al., 2022). The incorporation of different percentages of gallic acid
381 resulted in an increase in water vapor permeability, leading hydrogels with more porous
382 structure due to the existence of larger void spaces within the hydrogel that facilitate the
383 movement of water molecules (Table 1). This observation can be corroborated by the
384 inherent mesoporosity of other hydrogels, as documented in prior studies (Barboza-
385 Carmona et al., 2022). This hypothesis may explain the increased WVP permeability
386 achieved by alginate hydrogel loaded with 0.8% w/v of gallic acid ($3.4 \cdot 10^{-5}$ g/Kpa h m).
387 This fact might be especially relevant in applications where moisture transmission is
388 desirable, such as in some types of food packaging or dermal patches.

389 The swelling degree is another property of hydrogels that should be considered. The
390 incorporation of gallic acid into alginate-glycerol hydrogel lead a significant increase in
391 swelling ratio values (Table 1) being 1.7 in the base film up to 6.5 in functionalized films

392 with gallic acid. These results revealed that the obtained alginate hydrogels presented a
393 swelling capacity in range with previously reported in literature (Choi et al., 2022; Guan
394 et al., 2024). This fact seemed to be attributable to the chemical structure of gallic acid
395 whose hydroxyl groups can establish hydrogen bonds with water, leading to increased
396 water uptake and swelling of the hydrogels. This interaction seemed to precipitate an
397 increased water uptake and swelling of the alginate-based films, a phenomenon that had
398 been corroborated by existing literature (Shivakumara and Demappa, 2019). In the
399 aforementioned study, the swelling behavior of sodium alginate/poly (vinyl alcohol)
400 hydrogels was examined, and it was found that the degree of swelling was intimately tied
401 to the concentration of glutaraldehyde and the pH of the environment. However,
402 particularly in our study, the percentage of gallic acid used seemed to be insignificant in
403 these values. Therefore, the hypothesis that gains more strength is related to the amount
404 of hydroxyl groups provided by the gallic acid, thus causing an increase in the hydrogen
405 bonds between gel and water, rising the swelling ratio of functionalized hydrogels
406 compared to base hydrogel (Sharma et al., 2022).

407 3.1.2. Mechanical properties

408 Other mechanical properties assessed in the developed hydrogels was the ultimate
409 tensile strength. The hydrogel non-functionalized exhibited an ultimate tensile strength
410 of 2.2. MPa (Table 1). In this sense, the results were similar to those obtained by Chen *et*
411 *al* and Guan *et al* who developed alginate composite hydrogels with gelatine and
412 poly(vinylalcohol), respectively (Chen et al., 2023; Guan et al., 2024). The addition of
413 gallic acid at 0.1 and 0.5 % did not evidenced a significant change in the ability to resist
414 tensile forces. However, the ultimate tensile strength value significantly drops to 1.10
415 MPa at the highest percentage of gallic acid tested (0.8 %). This observation suggested
416 that the incorporation of great concentrations of gallic acid might be compromised the

417 tensile strength of the alginate hydrogels. Several papers support this observation,
418 indicating that gallic acid may interfere with the cross-linking within the alginate-glycerol
419 matrix, leading to reduced resistance to tensile forces (Giz et al., 2020; Russo et al., 2007;
420 Zhan et al., 2015). Some authors found that the combination of glycerol, used as
421 plasticizer, and calcium crosslinking had a synergistic effect on the mechanical properties
422 of alginate films (Giz et al., 2020). Other authors also observed changes in the physical
423 properties of alginate films after cross-linking with calcium ions, supporting the idea that
424 alterations in cross-linking can significantly affect the film's mechanical properties
425 (Russo et al., 2007). Gallic acid might be introducing structural irregularities or disrupting
426 intermolecular interactions within the hydrogel, as evidenced in the study by Zhan 2015,
427 which demonstrated the binding interaction between gallic acid and a carbohydrate
428 structure, indicates the potential of gallic acid to interfere with other substances and
429 networks, thereby weakening the overall structure and reducing the UTS (Zhan et al.,
430 2015). However, this potential disadvantage must be evaluated in the context of the final
431 application of these hydrogels. A lower tensile strength might not significantly impact the
432 film's performance, especially if tensile forces are not a key consideration in the
433 application. For instance, in applications like thermal insulation or moisture absorption
434 where tensile strength may not be the primary concern, the advantages of gallic acid
435 incorporation might outweigh the decrease in UTS.

436 It is worthy to note, that the differential impact of gallic acid on the tensile strength
437 and Young's modulus of alginate-glycerol hydrogels can be attributed to the complex
438 interplay of molecular interactions and structural rearrangements induced by the acid.
439 When gallic acid is incorporated, it may preferentially interact with specific components
440 of the alginate-glycerol matrix, leading to a localized disruption in the network structure.
441 This localized effect might cause a decrease in tensile strength as the structural integrity

442 at certain points within the matrix is compromised. However, the Young's modulus, a
443 measure of the material's inherent elasticity, remains unaffected (Table 1) because it is
444 largely dictated by the bulk properties of the material rather than localized structural
445 alterations. The macroscopic elastic behavior of the hydrogel encompasses a broader
446 structural framework, rendering it less sensitive to localized disruptions caused by the
447 introduction of gallic acid. The evaluation of mechanical properties, including the impact
448 of gallic acid incorporation on the Young's modulus, unveils insights into the nuanced
449 behavior of the material. A constant Young's modulus (≈ 5.4 MPa) across different gallic
450 acid concentrations implies that the material's inherent elastic properties are largely
451 unaffected by the introduction of gallic acid. The analysis is corroborated by a study
452 detailed by Essefi et al., 2020, where the mechanical properties of biocompatible
453 microparticles, including calcium alginate microbeads loaded with gallic acid, were
454 explored. Despite alterations in the network structure of hydrogels associated with
455 changes in UTS or WVP due to gallic acid incorporation, the overall elasticity of the
456 material remains constant. This phenomenon could be attributed to a balance struck
457 between the structural disruption instigated by gallic acid and a compensatory
458 mechanism, possibly akin to increased cross-linking density or modifications in
459 molecular interactions within the material. This balanced perspective aligns with the
460 findings from the referenced study, where calculations rooted in the linear character of
461 stresses and deformation revealed that the microbeads exhibited delayed elasticity (Essifi
462 et al., 2020). The consistency of Young's modulus measurements with direct experimental
463 findings underscores the resilience of the material's elastic properties, even amidst
464 variations induced by gallic acid incorporation. Such consistency in stiffness despite
465 variations in other properties may be advantageous for applications that require a stable
466 response to deformation. According to the obtained results, the elasticity of alginate based

467 hydrogels obtained in this study was in line with values collected from literature of
468 alginate based hydrogels (Bento et al., 2022) and quite higher to those developed with
469 alginate without any plasticizer (Essifi et al., 2020).

470 On the other hand, the incorporation of gallic acid significantly reduced the fracture
471 toughness (Table 1) which is a measure of resistance to fracture when a crack or other
472 stress-concentrating defect is present. Fracture toughness is indicative of a material's
473 resistance to the propagation of cracks. When gallic acid was incorporated, it may interact
474 with the polymeric chains and cross-linking bonds within the alginate-glycerol matrix in
475 a manner that specifically affected the material's behavior under stress and its ability to
476 resist crack propagation. The alginate hydrogel showed a toughness of 732 KJ/m³ which
477 were similar to those obtained by Guan et al. 2024. However, this parameter decreased
478 with the concentration of gallic acid introduced, reaching a value of 214 KJ/m³ for the
479 hydrogel with the highest gallic acid loading. This substantial reduction implied that the
480 addition of gallic acid made alginate-glycerol hydrogels more prone to fracture,
481 suggesting a more brittle structure. This could be due to the gallic acid causing changes
482 in the alginate-glycerol network, perhaps by disrupting the intermolecular bonds or
483 introducing structural irregularities, which could promote crack propagation and thereby
484 decrease the material's resistance to fracture. However, the reduction in fracture
485 toughness might not necessarily limit the potential application of hydrogel since in
486 applications where the hydrogel would be exposed to minimal mechanical stress or where
487 brittleness was not an important factor, this reduction in toughness might not be a
488 disadvantage.

489 3.1.3 Microstructure: moisture isotherm, porosity and HRSEM observation

490 On the surface characterization and porosity of the alginate-glycerol materials, BET
491 (Brunauer-Emmett-Teller) method is commonly used for the characterization of the

492 surface area of certain materials. These results provided essential insights into the
493 structural characteristics of the alginate-glycerol and gallic acid-functionalized hydrogels
494 (Table 1). It is important to note that the observed changes in pore radius across the
495 different hydrogels did not exhibit a substantial variation, even with the gallic acid
496 incorporation, where pore radius, was ranged from 1.52 to 1.72 nm. Additionally, the
497 surface area values were quite similar except for the hydrogel with 0.8% gallic acid,
498 which showed the highest specific surface area ($13.83 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$). Although the surface area
499 of these hydrogels were lower than similar alginate-based hydrogels previously reported
500 (Viganó et al., 2020; Martins et al., 2015), these findings suggested that the addition of
501 gallic acid led to an alteration in the structural properties of hydrogels in terms of surface
502 area but not in pore size. Previously, it had been reported that small changes in soft
503 calcium concentration (20 – 25 mM) in calcium-alginate hydrogels did not induce
504 changes in surface area, although the introduction oxidized or peptide-grafted alginate in
505 the gels resulted in larger pore sizes (Akbarzadeh Solbu et al., 2022). However, in this
506 study, it appears that the addition of gallic acid increases the porosity of the hydrogels.
507 These results helped to explain the mechanical behavior of this hydrogel, since having
508 higher porosity, the fracture propagation was facilitated and, hence, the fracture toughness
509 value was lower. The same can be observed with the low UTS value obtained in the tensile
510 tests as well as WVP assays. This behavior reinforces the hypothesis described in the
511 previous sections. In spite of these results, the information provided by the high-
512 resolution scanning electron microscopy (HRSEM) showed homogeneous surfaces of
513 alginate hydrogels and those functionalized with different concentration of gallic acid
514 (Figure 1).

515

516

517

518

519 Figure 1: HRSEM micrographs of alginate and gallic acid-functionalized alginate
 520 hydrogels: alginate-glycerol (93:7) (A); alginate-glycerol (93:7) with 0.1 % of gallic acid
 521 (B); alginate-glycerol (93:7) with 0.5 % of gallic acid (C); alginate-glycerol (93:7) with
 522 0.8 % of gallic acid (D) and its cross section (E)

523

524 The lack of significant disparities in surface morphology may confirm the pore radius
 525 data since the values were similar in all the hydrogels tested. However, the SEM images
 526 did not explain the increase in surface area, since the resolution of the technique applied
 527 to the structural images obtained made it difficult to visualize pores with such a small size
 528 and, therefore, did not allow verification of these results. Further study of the hydrogels
 529 obtained by cryogenic fracture, particularly on the cross sections, provide more detailed
 530 insights into the microstructural features, and the homogeneity of the hydrogel matrix.
 531 Notably, in the hydrogels with the highest concentration of gallic acid (0.8%), the SEM
 532 images revealed the presence of gallic acid crystals forming within the structure (Figure

533 1E). These crystals are clearly visible and indicate a significant interaction between the
534 gallic acid and the hydrogel matrix, particularly at higher concentrations. This
535 crystallization could potentially impact the mechanical and functional properties of the
536 hydrogels, providing a unique insight into the material's behavior and performance.

537 3.1.4. Thermal stability

538 On the other hand, an analysis of the thermal properties of impregnated alginate-
539 glycerol hydrogels functionalized with gallic acid, is imperative to understand how these
540 additives can influence material performance under varying temperature conditions.
541 Upon investigating the thermal behavior of the impregnated alginate-glycerol hydrogel
542 with gallic acid, it was evident that their profiles shared similarities with the raw alginate-
543 glycerol (Figure 2).

544

545 Figure 2: Thermogravimetric analysis of alginate and gallic acid-functionalized alginate
546 aerogels in nitrogen atmosphere.

547 However, there are some discernible differences. The initial endothermic peak in the
548 curve (approximately at 150°C), which typically represents an energy-absorbing process,
549 is less profound in the case of the hydrogel impregnated with gallic acid. This could
550 suggest that the addition of gallic acid to the matrix could be influencing the initial
551 thermal events experienced by the hydrogel. Additionally, a prominent observation is the
552 overlap of the second exothermic peak (between 200°C and 280°C) (indicative of
553 decomposition) with the endothermic peak associated with the melting of gallic acid. This
554 superimposition suggests that there's a concurrent process of gallic acid melting and
555 hydrogel decomposition. The close association of these thermal events could indicate that
556 the decomposition of the alginate-glycerol matrix and the melting of the gallic acid are
557 intertwined. Perhaps, the interaction between gallic acid and the matrix is such that the
558 decomposition of the hydrogel facilitates or is accelerated by the melting of gallic acid.
559 Similar observations on the thermal stability of alginate-based hydrogels were reported,
560 reinforcing the findings presented (Dos Santos et al., 2020).

561 3.1.5 FT-IR spectra

562 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) was used to discern potential
563 chemical interactions between gallic acid and the constituents of the alginate-glycerol
564 hydrogels. The distinct FTIR spectra for alginate hydrogel and those loaded with gallic
565 acid can be seen in Figure 3.

566

567

568

569

570

571 Figure 3: FTIR spectrum of alginate and gallic acid-functionalized alginate hydrogels.

572

573 Distinct peaks of gallic acid, noticeable at 3300 cm^{-1} , were believed to arise due to
 574 the aromatic and carboxylic O-H stretching, which underscores the presence of the
 575 hydroxyl groups (-OH) in the third, fourth, and fifth positions of the aromatic rings (Alfei
 576 et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2021). An emerging band at 1683 cm^{-1} could be attributed to
 577 the C=O stretching vibration associated with the carboxylic acid that is characteristic of
 578 phenolic compounds (Alfei et al., 2020). Additionally, bands at 1610 and 1410 cm^{-1}
 579 appear to correspond to the C=C aromatic stretching vibration (Alfei et al., 2020).
 580 Notably, there was minimal difference between the FTIR spectra of the gallic acid-free
 581 hydrogels and those impregnated with gallic acid, suggesting that slight chemical

582 interactions transpired between the hydrogel matrix and gallic acid since the interaction
583 between polymeric chains and gallic acid formed by hydrogen bridges. This suggested
584 that the biological activity of gallic acid could remained preserved even when it was
585 integrated with the alginate-glycerol matrix. This observation was consistent with
586 research outcomes from the literature (Gan and Chin, 2021), which also found no
587 discernible interactions between bioactive constituents and polymers, ensuring the
588 preservation of the bioactivity of the constituents.

589 3.2. Optical characterization of hydrogels.

590 Apart from physicochemical properties, other hydrogels features should be taken
591 into account since for some applications the appearance and the color characteristics of
592 hydrogels can be decisive. Although hydrogels based on polysaccharides are usually
593 transparent, the addition of certain substances for their functionalization can modify
594 optical properties (Biao et al., 2019; Dou et al., 2018). In our case, the alginate-glycerol
595 hydrogel exhibited transmittance of 90 %, and a low opacity value, 1.7 (Table 2). As
596 consequence of the addition of gallic acid, the higher percentage was, the less
597 transmittance showed the functionalized hydrogel. Transmittances of 80, 60 and 55 %
598 were detected in the alginate hydrogels with 0.1, 0.5 and 0.8 % of gallic acid respectively,
599 which were significant different among them. A contrary behavior was detected for
600 opacity which significantly increased according to the gallic acid concentration: 2.1 in
601 hydrogel with 0.1 % of gallic acid, 2.3 in hydrogel with 0.5 % of gallic acid and 2.7 in
602 the hydrogel performed with the highest gallic acid percentage. Consequently, it should
603 be stated that the addition of gallic acid drove to hydrogels less transparent and opaquer.
604 Similar results were observed in edible alginate hydrogels loaded with tea polyphenol
605 extract, whose opacities increased with the increment of polyphenol content and less light
606 was transmitted through the films (Biao et al., 2019). However, no significant differences

607 were found in the color parameters (L^* , a^* , b^* , ΔE) in the functionalization of hydrogels
 608 with gallic acid incorporation. However, it is important to take into consideration that the
 609 use of other phenolic substances, especially phenolic extracts derived from food or plants,
 610 can substantially modify the appearance resulting in highly coloured hydrogels as the
 611 extract concentration is increased (Biao et al., 2019; Dou et al., 2018).

612

613

614 Table 2. Optical properties of alginate and gallic acid-functionalized alginate hydrogels

615

Aerogels	Transmittance %	Opacity	L^*	a^*	b^*	ΔE	Photography
Alg-Gly (93:7)	90 ± 2^a	1.7 ± 0.1^a	43 ± 1^a	-0.31 ± 0.04^a	1.4 ± 0.2^a	-	
Alg-Gly (93:7), Gallic acid 0.1 %	80 ± 2^b	2.1 ± 0.2^b	44 ± 3^a	-0.35 ± 0.02^a	1.6 ± 0.1^a	1.7 ± 0.4	
Alg-Gly (93:7), Gallic acid 0.5 %	60 ± 2^c	2.3 ± 0.1^b	43 ± 1^a	-0.29 ± 0.01^a	1.3 ± 0.1^a	1.8 ± 0.5	
Alg-Gly (93:7), Gallic acid 0.8 %	55 ± 2^d	2.7 ± 0.1^c	42 ± 1^a	-0.33 ± 0.02^a	1.5 ± 0.1^a	1.8 ± 0.3	

616 Alg: Alginate; Gly: Glycerol; ΔE : Colour difference between alginate and gallic acid-
 617 functionalised alginate hydrogels.

618 Values with different superscripts in the same column denote significant differences among
 619 aerogels according to the Tukey post-hoc analysis ($p \leq 0.05$) when variances were homogenous,
 620 or according to T3 Dunnet post-hoc analysis ($p \leq 0.05$) for non-homogenous variances.

621

622

623

624 3.3. Functional characterization of hydrogels.

625 Gallic acid with three hydroxyl groups is proven to have strong radical-scavenging
 626 activity (Sroka and Cisowski, 2003). For this reason, gallic acid has been used in this
 627 study as antioxidant agent with the aim of functionalize sustainable macromolecular
 628 scaffolds based on alginate hydrogels.

629 The incorporation of gallic acid raised the total phenolic content of the alginate
 630 hydrogel by gradually increasing the concentration (Table 3). The strong correlation
 631 among total phenol content and antioxidant capacity has been widely claimed (Alañón,
 632 et al., 2011a; 2011b) suggesting that polyphenols are the main contributors to antioxidant
 633 activity.

634

635 Table 3. Total phenol content (TPC) and antioxidant activity measured by DPPH and
 636 FRAP methods of gallic acid-functionalized alginate hydrogels.

Hydrogels	Total phenol content	Antioxidant activity	
	TPC (mg _{gallic acid} /g _{aerogel})	DPPH (mg _{gallic acid} /g _{aerogel})	FRAP (mmol _{FeSO4} /g _{aerogel})
Alg-Gly (93:7)	-	-	-
Alg-Gly (93:7), Gallic acid 0.1 %	6.0 ± 0.4 ^c	6.6 ± 0.5 ^c	0.19 ± 0.01 ^c
Alg-Gly (93:7), Gallic acid 0.5 %	23 ± 1 ^b	32 ± 2 ^b	0.84 ± 0.04 ^b
Alg-Gly (93:7), Gallic acid 0.8 %	45.1 ± 0.3 ^a	46 ± 3 ^a	1.4 ± 0.1 ^a

637 Alg: Alginate; Gly: Glycerol.

638 Values with different superscripts in the same column denote significant differences
 639 among aerogels according to the Tukey post-hoc analysis ($p \leq 0.05$) when variances were
 640 homogenous, or according to T3 Dunnet post-hoc analysis ($p \leq 0.05$) for non-
 641 homogenous variances.

642

643 Due to a comprehensive evaluation of antioxidant capacity requires the use of several
644 methods based on different chemistry principle, two methods with different mechanisms
645 for inhibiting oxidation were employed. In this sense, although both chosen methods are
646 based on a single electron transfer reaction, in DPPH method, the DPPH[•] radical is
647 reduced by antioxidants meanwhile in FRAP method, is a metal (Fe³⁺) reduced into Fe²⁺
648 by electrons donated by antioxidants. DPPH and FRAP methods provided consistent and
649 complementary results, as both methods confirmed that the antioxidant properties of
650 alginate hydrogels improved with increasing gallic acid incorporation (Table 3). The
651 addition of 0.1% of gallic acid into alginate hydrogel increased the total phenol content
652 up to 6.0 mg_{gallic acid}/g_{hydrogel} which implied an antioxidant activity of 6.6 mg_{gallic acid}/g_{hydrogel}
653 and 0.19 mmol_{FeSO4}/g_{hydrogel} according to DPPH and FRAP methods, respectively.
654 Antioxidant values were increased about 4.8 and 4.4-fold with the addition of 0.5 % of
655 gallic acid into alginate hydrogels. These values were greatly improved when the
656 maximum concentration of gallic acid tested was incorporated. The ability to scavenge
657 free radicals of hydrogels loaded with 0.8 % of gallic acid was enhanced around 7.0-fold
658 and 7.3-fold in DPPH and FRAP methods, respectively, compared with those hydrogels
659 loaded with the minimum percentage of gallic acid tested, reaching values of 46.0 mg_{gallic}
660 acid/g_{hydrogel} and 1.40 mmol_{FeSO4}/g_{hydrogel}. Although several studies have confirmed the
661 increase of antioxidant properties of films by adding polyphenols, differences in
662 measurements of antioxidant activity determined by non-standardized methods with
663 different protocols and ways to express the results make difficult the comparison with
664 those reported in literature. The addition of 5.0 % of tea polyphenols extract to sodium
665 alginate films increase antioxidant activity about 7.1-fold according to DPPH method and
666 a 41.0-fold when ABTS assay was used (Biao et al., 2019). Previously, lower percentages
667 of tea polyphenols (0.4 – 2.0 %) were also loaded into gelatin sodium alginate films

668 exhibiting an increase of antioxidant activity around 2.52-fold (DPPH) and 1.54-fold
669 (ABTS) (Dou et al., 2018). Therefore, it seems that lower percentage of gallic acid are
670 required to functionalize hydrogels compared with the polyphenol extract doses used with
671 the same purposes.

672 In addition, the release of gallic acid of functionalized hydrogels in phosphate-buffer
673 saline for 24 hours at 37°C was monitored (Figure 4).

674

675

676 **Figure 4:** Release of gallic acid from functionalized hydrogels in phosphate-buffer
677 saline for 24 hours by means of antioxidant activity measurement based on DPPH
678 method.

679

680 The release of gallic acid appeared to be dose-dependent, meaning the higher was the
681 gallic acid percentage used in the functionalize hydrogel formulation, the higher release.
682 According to the results, it seems that, regardless of the percentage of gallic acid loaded
683 into the hydrogel, the shape of the release profile was similar for all hydrogels, with a
684 rapid release at the beginning reaching the maximum amount of gallic acid released
685 within one to two hours. Subsequently, gallic acid release gradually decreased over time.
686 This reduction in concentration of gallic acid, may be due to the interaction between the
687 gallic acid released by the gel and the sodium salts present in the medium, it caused the
688 formation of gallic acid salts, such as sodium gallate, whose antioxidant activity is lower
689 (Cláudio et al., 2012). For this reason, the antioxidant activity decreases with time after
690 the maximum release peak (1-2 h). These results make it possible to establish the
691 maximum duration of application of these devices for the controlled and localized release
692 of the bioactive component, as well as the dose released over time. Thanks to these results,
693 these devices could be postulated as a sustainable, effective, and promising alternative for
694 controlled and localized release of bioactive compounds.

695

696 **4. Conclusions**

697 Gallic acid-enhanced alginate hydrogels offer a sustainable and distinctive material
698 to be used as plastic replacement in food packaging. The addition of gallic acid improved
699 the mechanical and functional properties, as well as biodegradability of hydrogels which
700 entails a significant advancement in the field of sustainable biomaterials for food
701 packaging.

702 In general terms, thickness, opacity, water vapor permeability and swelling degree
703 were increased as consequence of gallic acid incorporation. In addition, the

704 functionalization of alginate hydrogels with gallic acid made them hydrogels with less
705 resistant to tensile forces and crack propagation due to the increased porosity, especially
706 those loaded with the maximum concentration of gallic acid tested (0.8 %), although
707 elasticity remained unaffected. However, it should be highlighted that the incorporation
708 of gallic acid increased antioxidant activity of alginate hydrogels by 7.0 – 7.3 times at
709 higher loading concentration.

710 Understanding these underlying structural, mechanical, and functional changes offer
711 valuable insights for customizing hydrogels with tailor properties to be more effectively
712 for their intended application. Such a diverse range of insights will help in developing a
713 nuanced perspective on the multifaceted impacts of gallic acid incorporation on the
714 mechanical and antioxidant properties of this sustainable macromolecular scaffolds based
715 on functionalized alginate hydrogels to be considered in their design and development
716 depending on their application. Particularizing each of these circumstances will help to
717 pave the way for upcoming investigations in their application in packaging of real
718 samples.

719

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726 **6. Data Availability Statement**

727 The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding
728 author upon reasonable request.

729 **7. Conflict of Interest Statement**

730 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
731 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

732

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